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CAREER ORIENTATION AS A DETERMINANT FOR CAREER CHOICE IN LIBRARIANSHIP AMONG FINAL YEAR STUDENTS IN FEDERAL UNITY SCHOOLS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Choosing a career that aligns with student's interests, skills and values considerably increases their chances of socio-economic accomplishment, personal satisfaction and overall happiness in life. The study investigated career orientation as a determinant for career choice in librarianship among final year students in federal unity schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The study populations were 937 final year students in Federal Unity Schools, Lagos State. 50 percent of the entire population was used bringing the sample size to 468 respondents. Questionnaire was the data collection instrument, data collected were analysed using SPSS version 24 and results were presented in frequency table using percentage count, mean and standard deviation. The study found that the overall mean of career orientation of student was "33.37" and it was concluded that the level of career orientation of final year students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria was average. Also, the overall mean of career choice in librarianship was "28.39" which indicates average level of career choice in librarianship among final year students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The test of hypotheses showed a positive linear relationship between career orientation and career choice among final year students in Federal Unity schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study concluded that career choice in librarianship is dependent on extensive career orientation of secondary school students. It was recommended that qualified professionals in librarianship and guidance and counselling should be engaged to help the students take advantage of the numerous opportunities that abound in librarianship profession among others.

KEYWORDS

Career Orientation, Career Choice, Librarianship, Final Year Students, Federal Unity Schools.

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Introduction

Senior Secondary school years are critical for students to begin preparation for life after high school. This is because most secondary school students have little or no information about the subject combinations they wish to study in higher education. Career orientation programmes will help them to make a better career decisions. A career orientation programmes is necessary to ensure that students understand the subject combinations and what it entails before deciding on a career path in a particular field. Most students do not have access to expert vocational and career orientation programmes during their secondary school transitions. Because there are no good careers orientation programmes available, most students choose careers based on variables such as family, peer and teachers influence.

Career orientation at schools involves conversations between teachers (subject specialist) and students on real-life experiences that are future-oriented by highlighting the presence of career competencies among students. It is meant to assist students to think on their goals, interests, credentials and talents. In addition to their additional education, training or work, it has an impact on their social lives, finances, families and health consequences (Loan and Van 2015). They further stated that secondary schools are critical in preparing students to successfully transition to a future career path. Giving students prospective or curricular chances to improve their general competences, support their interests and ambitions and assist them in choosing a professional route is one example. Students are more involved in their education and extremely motivated about their future when they have a full perception of themselves and how they might live and work in the future.

In order to prepare students for their future, high-quality career orientation services is an important aspect of their education. It assists them in comprehending the labour market and educational system, as well as relating their life demands and becoming responsible global citizens. Sovet and Metz (2014) stated that as the students near the end of their high school years, they face a slew of personal decisions that can have far-reaching and long-term consequences. Some of these choices are career-related, such as finding a job, acquiring an apprenticeship, attending college, selecting a career or earning experience through volunteer work, among others. Fortunately, students are not alone in making these career selections; students who are assisted in making effective transitions from secondary school to higher study, training, or employment gain economically and socially. In secondary schools, career orientation has a significant role in supporting students' interests, strengths and goals.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2002) hinted on areas where such orientation empowers. These includes assisting individuals in developing greater self-awareness in areas such as interests, values, capabilities and personality style; connecting students to sources where they can learn more about professions and occupations; and engaging students in the discussion process so that they can choose a career path. Savickas (2011) added that career orientation is the process of meaning co-construction in which the counsellor engages in the client's experience, allowing the client to freely express his or her subjectivity while investigating, developing meanings and constructing new representations.

However, the two major components of career orientation are career counselling and career information and literatures will be reviewed in these areas. Meanwhile, it has been observed that school librarians do not play motivational roles to students; they do not show self- directedness, career success, fulfillment and enthusiasm in the profession and thus could not stair positive attitude towards

the profession. Many of these librarians do not also provide career orientation which could help students to understand themselves, get vocational training and make career decisions in librarianship. It is on this milieu that the researchers investigate career orientation as a determinant for career choice in librarianship among final year students in federal unity schools in Lagos State, Nigeria

Research Questions

The study will focus on the following research questions:

1. What is the level of career orientation among final year students in federal unity schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of career choices in librarianship among final year students in federal unity schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The null hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance in the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between career orientation and career choice in librarianship among final year students in federal unity schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Career orientation is an ongoing face-to-face contact between counsellor and client, rather than a rigorous, rational process with the relationship between counsellor and client performing an important function. Watts and Kidd (2000) explained that career orientation involves a number of approaches that enable individuals to make informed decisions about their educational, occupational and personal development. In a complex and constantly changing world, career orientation aims to help students understand themselves by providing professional assistance with educational, vocational, emotional and personal social decisions. Watts and Fretwell (2004) acknowledged that career orientation and counselling services empower individuals of any age and at any stage of their life to make educational, training and vocational decisions and manage their careers.

In Nigeria, there is a widespread belief that career orientation in schools consists of teachers speaking generally without providing thorough guidance and then allowing students to choose any career they want. Career counselling is frequently used to provide career information and aid to students both generally and particularly on career choice and its possibilities Egbo (2015).

The author further detailed that career counselling facilitates career choice, career development, preparing for and entering a job, being aware of occupations, being aware of factors influencing job choice, availability and utilisation of occupational information. It also involves interpretation of psychological tests relating to jobs, understanding the job environment of localities and increasing the relevance of occupational information.

Ombaba, Keraro, Sindabi and Asiayo (2014) affirmed that career information programmes are designed to assist students recognise their potentials and maximize them. The authors believe that the school career information programmes will offer students with professional services that will support them in making sophisticated career decisions. Students can use career information to help themselves in making career decisions, manage their careers and progress from a general grasp of life and work to a more detailed understanding of the realistic study and employment alternatives available to them. Assisting students in making well-informed decisions on subjects and disciplines can lead to a more

positive outlook on life, a greater sense of purpose and a higher degree of contribution to their families and society.

Omoni (2009) detailed that when clients are fully informed, they are competent of making their own decisions and counsellors do not need to advise or tell them what to do anymore. Ibrahim, Olaka, Wambiya and Raburu (2014) noted that career orientation is generally recognised as significant and successful technique of bridging the gap between school and the workplace. It strives to help students understand themselves and is aimed to provide specialised assistance with educational, vocational, emotional and personal social decisions in a complicated and changing world. Ogundele and Feyisetan (2014) indicated that each school should have a suitable career orientation and counselling clinic where the students can be counselled on their career choices to avoid future regrets, as well as periodically hold career seminars to expose students to various alternatives.

Many students lose focus and engage in bad behaviours such as drug abuse, smoking alcoholism, truancy and other juvenile delinquencies (Boitt, 2016) which are recognized as major factors responsible for early school drop-out, poor grades and ineffectiveness on future jobs and general difficulties in career development. According to the Ministry of Education (MoE, 2010), the most difficult challenge of students in senior four (S4) and senior five (S5) is deciding on an acceptable school and subject combination, which is related to poor career selection and preparation. Other factors such as career teacher/counsellor to students' ratio, which is 1:500 in East Africa (Ayiro 2016) and 1:1000 in Nigerian schools (Kiweewa, Knettel and Luke, 2017).

Wambu and Fischer (2015) revealed that uncertainty and lack of career orientation materials were major challenges to career orientation and counselling in schools. Anagbogu and Nwokolo (2010), Oraegbunam (2008) and Low (2009) revealed that the greatest problem to orientation practice in schools is the lack of counselling timetable, among other things. Oye, Obi, Mohd and Gwadabawa (2012) revealed that most schools do not have value for orientation and counselling services. They disclosed that the terms were designed without specifying a time frame for students to get formal assistance and counselling from professional counsellors or selected teachers. Lack of sufficient space and time to conduct orientation were also identified as major obstacle by (Mushaandja, Haihambo, Vergnani and Frank, 2013).

On the contrary, the findings Mvungin (2009) and Mbilinyi (2012) reported that the educational system in Tanzania did not provide proper career guidance and counselling to the majority of students. This indicates a low level of career orientation for the students. Furthermore, the analysis of career orientation of the study by Mvungin (2009) and Mbilinyi (2012) showed that the majority of students receive general information and orientation about social welfare and university policies once they join the university and that little information is given to them with regards to orientation and the requisite courses.

King (2003) studied career orientations among young graduates in the United Kingdom. The author found that the endorsement of the 'new career' was limited. In line with these results, Pitcher and Purcell (2018) and Sturges, Guest and Machenzie (2000) found that United Kingdom graduates still had very high expectations of organisational career management despite the current rhetoric about career self-management.

Also, the study by Mayrhofer, Meyer et al (2006) showed a sample of Austrian graduates that a preference for a traditional career was still widespread. Likewise, Grote and Raeder (2009) reported a

prevalence of traditional career orientations in Switzerland. Maingi and Wasanga (2011) also attested to the fact that lack of awareness about what happens at the universities by many secondary school students limits their university course selection and career decision-making process as a whole indicating a low level of career orientation.

Furthermore, it has been detected that many students join higher institutions with little or no idea about the career path to pursue. As a result, many students have struggled through their first and second years of higher education and a majority of them may have to change their courses. This could be due to lack of career orientation, counselling and lack of appropriate awareness of where they are going to or what they want to do with their life among others. Quadri (2018) added that a number of library science students in Nigeria enrolled in library school after failing to gain admission into their first choice disciplines such as law, engineering among others.

The findings of Ismail (2012) revealed that after assessing the perceptions of higher secondary students regarding librarianship as career choice, as well as their level of awareness and interest in librarianship as a career choice, it was discovered that the majority of students are unaware of the field of library science and rank librarianship as the least desirable career option. The author added that school librarians should work harder to promote the librarianship profession as a favourable career option. In agreement with the finding, the study conducted by Damilola, Ajayi, and Adetayo (2018) discovered that majority of students do not have an interest in library and information science as a career, but they found themselves in it by chance and while they eventually enjoy the course, they would have preferred to choose something else.

The study by Busayo (2006) did not fail to establish the true state of things in terms of the choice of librarianship as a career for high school students. The study was carried out on a total of 1228 students from eight Nigerian LIS schools. It was found, that the majority of the respondents learned about library science from their mentors, parents and relatives. This submission leaves a bitter pill in the mouth to swallow for those in the librarianship profession as it shows that it is hardly a first choice career for any student.

Issa and Nwalo (2008) who reported that the bulk of the students (61.6%) did not choose the LIS programme as their first choice, they ended up as a last option in library schools. Also, in line with findings of the study, Igbinosa (2007) noted that people, particularly students, do not want to pursue a profession in librarianship. This is due to their ignorance of the reality that librarians are the brains behind every other discipline's success story. Salaam and Owolabi (2010) suggested that in order to attract more secondary school graduates into librarianship, library science should be taught in all Nigerian secondary schools and the Librarian's Registration Council alongside Nigerian Library Association should launch a full-scale public awareness campaign about librarianship as a noble profession.

Kimiti and Mwova (2012) noted the dilemma of career choice among secondary school students by establishing a significant relationship between career orientation and career choice. It was further revealed that students make their career choices based on the information they received from the career counsellor or teachers. Their findings affirmed that the provision of career orientation services positively influenced students' decision on their career choice. The results from the study conducted by Racho, Wambiya, Aloka and Raburu (2014) concur with their study and affirmed that students' career awareness had significant relationship with students' career decisions. Another study by Lugulu and Musoga (2013) found that career orientation provided in schools was inadequate to enable

students make informed career choices. Since the success of students making informed degree programmes choices depends on the level of career awareness.

Gitonga (2013) admitted that insufficiently prepared teachers and poorly equipped career guidance resources were the causes of career decisiveness among students in secondary schools. In the same vein, Yusuf's (2019) earlier study agreed that limited knowledge of occupations and range of alternatives available often leads to unrealistic career aspirations. Garnesby (2013) concluded that adequate career information resources and provision of professional career guidance and counselling at all education levels and direct or indirect exposure to work experiences from early stages of life play a vital role in career development.

Students especially those in senior secondary schools are expected to build a career path after their secondary education and choosing a career is one of the major challenge confronting them. Literatures and observations have shown that many students who gained admission into university and studying librarianship did not choose the course as a career. They found themselves in the discipline after failing to gain admission into their first choice discipline. The lack of interest and ultimately lack of choice in librarianship as a profession among secondary students could be as a result lack of career orientation by the school librarians, as many of them could not inspire the students to understand themselves, get vocational training and make career choices in librarianship. It is on this framework that the study investigates career orientation as a dynamism for career interest in librarianship among selected senior secondary school students in Federal Unity Schools, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Descriptive research design was adopted for the study. The targeted population comprised 937 final year students in the four Federal Unity schools, Lagos State, Nigeria. A sampling size of 50 percent was used to bring the population to 469 and that was used for the study. Questionnaire was the instrument of data collection. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for data analysis. Results were presented in frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation. While hypothesis was tested with multiple regression analysis.

Presentation and Interpretation of Results

A total number of 469 copies of the questionnaire were administered to final year students in the four (4) Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. 436 were returned and found useful for the analysis, giving a response rate of 93%.

Table 1. Career orientation among final year students in federal unity schools in LagosState, Nigeria.

S/N	CAREER ORIENTATION	SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	St.D
1	Career orientation has helped me to have a clearer views about my future career choice	199 (45.6%)	175 (40.1%)	43 (9.9%)	19 (4.4%)	3.27	.8109
2	I feel excited about discussing my future career with the career counsellor	143 (32.8%)	185 (42.4%)	84 (19.3%)	24 (5.5%)	3.02	.8613
3	Career orientation has helped me to have a clearer understanding about other career options.	143 (32.8%)	181 (41.5%)	78 (17.9%)	34 (7.8%)	2.99	.9058
4	Career orientation programme and opportunities does not exist in my school.	58 (13.3%)	85 (19.5%)	141 (32.3%)	152 (34.9%)	2.11	1.0322
5	Career orientation has helped me to gain career information from objective source	143 (32.8%)	215 (49.3%)	57 (13.1%)	21 (4.8%)	3.10	.8016
6	Career orientation programme has made me to discover my academic strength and weaknesses	144 (33%)	196 (45%)	77 (17.7%)	19 (4.4%)	3.06	.8236
7	Career orientation has helped me to gain basic knowledge about my career choice	164 (37.6%)	203 (46.6%)	50 (11.5%)	19 (4.4%)	3.17	.7976
8	Career orientation has made me to developed the right attitude towards making a career choice	133 (30.5%)	242 (55.5%)	46 (10.6%)	15 (3.4%)	3.13	.7295
9	Career orientation has made me to know what is essentially requirements in the world of works	125 (28.7%)	206 (47.2%)	78 (17.9%)	27 (6.2%)	2.98	.8453
10	Career orientation has made me to realise that I will be responsible for my career success or failure	184 (42.2%)	184 (42.2%)	51 (11.7%)	17 (3.9%)	3.22	.8030
11	Career orientation has made me to understand that gender is not a factor in making a career choice	219 (50.2%)	157 (36%)	41 (9.4%)	19 (4.4%)	3.32	.8179

The above table shows the career orientation of students in Federal Unity schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The results of the study showed that career orientation has helped them to have clearer views about their future career choice ($\bar{x}$ =3.27; std dev. =.8109); they feel excited about discussing their future career with the career counsellor ($\bar{x}$ =3.02; std dev. =.8613); career orientation has helped them to have clearer understanding about other career options ($\bar{x}$ =2.99; std dev. =.9058); career orientation programme and opportunities do not exist in their school ($\bar{x}$ =2.11; std dev. =1.0322); career orientation has helped them to gain career information from objective sources ($\bar{x}$ =3.10; std dev. =.8016); career orientation programme has made them to discover their academic strength and weaknesses ($\bar{x}$ =3.06; std dev. B=.8236); career orientation has helped them to gain basic knowledge about their career choice ($\bar{x}$ =3.17; std dev. =.7976); career orientation has made them to develop the right attitude towards making a career choice ($\bar{x}$ =3.13; std dev. =.7295); career orientation has made them to know what is essentially requirements in the world of works ($\bar{x}$ =2.98; std dev. =.8453); career orientation has made them to realise that they will be responsible for their career success or failure ($\bar{x}$ =3.22; std dev. =.8030); career orientation has made them to understand that gender is not a factor in making a career choice ($\bar{x}$ =3.32; std dev. =.8179).

In order to establish the level of career orientation of final year student, a test of norm was conducted, results showed that scale between “1-29.3” indicates low; 29.4 - 58.6 indicates average level, while 58.7 - 88 indicates high level of career orientation. The overall mean of career orientation of student was “33.37”. It can therefore be concluded that the level of career orientation of final year students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria is average.

Table 2: Level of Career choice in librarianship among final year students in federal unity schools in Lagos State, Nigeria.

S/N	CAREER CHOICE IN LIBRARIANSHIP	SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	St.D
1	I am very sure of making a career choice in librarianship	74 (17 %)	44 (10.1%)	134 (30.7%)	184 (42.2%)	2.01	1.0973
2	I will choose librarianship due to my interest in the profession	44 (10.1%)	78 (17.9%)	141 (32.3%)	173 (39.7%)	1.98	.9906
3	I will choose librarianship as a choice of career because it has been recommended by my teachers, family members and friends.	49 (11.2%)	33 (7.6%)	162 (37.2%)	192 (44%)	1.86	.9737
4	I will choose librarianship as a profession because librarians have good social status in the society	36 (8.3%)	56 (12.8%)	166 (38.1%)	178 (40.8%)	1.88	.9250
5	I will choose librarianship as a profession because there is employment opportunities for everyone that studies the discipline	42 (9.6%)	61 (14%)	183 (42%)	150 (34.4%)	1.99	.9333
6	I will choose librarianship as a profession because as a librarian, there is prospect of a good salary	41 (9.4%)	65 (14.9%)	182 (41.7%)	148 (33.9%)	2.00	.9309
7	In librarianship profession, everyone enjoys strong job security	40 (9.2%)	83 (19%)	181 (41.5%)	132 (30.3%)	2.07	.9257
8	I think librarianship is a perfect profession for personality trait	43 (22%)	96 (22%)	156 (35.8%)	141 (32.3%)	2.09	.9650
9	I will chose librarianship because librarians enjoys holidays, leaves, insurance and retirement plans	41 (9.4%)	69 (15.8%)	186 (42.7%)	140 (32.1%)	2.02	.9256
10	Based on what I have heard, it will be pleasurable to study librarianship	45 (10.3%)	68 (15.6%)	181 (41.5%)	142 (32.6%)	2.03	.9461
11	Librarianship is the mother of all discipline.	44 (10.1%)	88 (20.2%)	173 (39.7%)	131 (30%)	2.10	.9473
12	Librarianship profession will be suited to my individual needs and student expectations.	43 (9.9%)	86 (19.7%)	171 (39.2%)	136 (31.2%)	2.08	.9481
13	I know I can succeed in life as a librarian	39 (8.9%)	66 (15.1%)	188 (43.1%)	143 (32.8%)	2.00	.9160
14	Librarians have a decent working hours and attractive surrounding	56 (12.8%)	116 (26.6%)	162 (37.2%)	102 (23.4%)	2.28	.9656

Table 4.7 showed the career choice in librarianship among students in Federal Unity schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The results of the study showed that they are very sure of making a career choice in librarianship ($\bar{x}$ =2.01; std dev. =1.097); they will choose librarianship due to their interest in the profession ($\bar{x}$ =1.98; std dev. =.9906); they will choose librarianship because of others' recommendation (teachers, family, friends, etc.) ($\bar{x}$ =1.86; std dev. =.9737); they will choose librarianship as a profession because librarians have good social status in the society ($\bar{x}$ =1.88; std dev. =.9250); they will choose librarianship because there is employment opportunities for everyone that studies the course ($\bar{x}$ =1.98; std dev. =.9333); they will choose librarianship because as a librarian, there is prospect of a good salary ($\bar{x}$ =1.99; std dev. =.9309); in librarianship profession, everyone enjoys strong job security ($\bar{x}$ =2.07; std dev. =.9257); they think librarianship is a perfect profession for their personality trait ($\bar{x}$ =2.09; std dev. =.9650); they will choose librarianship because librarians enjoys holidays, leaves, insurance and retirement plans ($\bar{x}$ =2.02; std dev. =.9256); based on what they have heard, it will be pleasurable to study librarianship ($\bar{x}$ =2.03; std dev. =.9461);

librarianship is the mother of all discipline ($\bar{x}$ =2.10; std dev. =.9473); librarianship profession will be suited to their individual needs and student expectations ($\bar{x}$ =2.08; std dev. =.9481); they know they can succeed in life as a librarian ($\bar{x}$ =2.00; std dev. =.9160); librarians have a decent working hours and attractive surrounding ($\bar{x}$ =2.28; std dev. =.9656).

In order to establish the level of career choice in librarianship of student, a test of norm was conducted, results showed that scale between “1-26.6” is low; 26.7 – 53.2 indicates average level, while 53.2 – 80 indicates high level of career choice. The overall mean of career choice of student is “28.39”. It can therefore be concluded that the level of career choice in librarianship among students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria is average.

Table 3: Relationship between career orientation and career choice in librarianship among final year students infederal unity schools in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	St.Dev	Df	R	P	Sig
Career orientation	436	64.24	9.63	436	.370	.000	S
Career choice	436	40.88	13.97				

The above table shows the relationship between career orientation and career choice in librarianship among final year students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The table shows that career orientation (r =.370 p < 0.05; N = 436) has a significant positive relationship with career choice in librarianship among final year students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. This implies that there is positive linear relationship between career orientation and career choice among final year students in Federal Unity schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. This also implies that an increase in career orientation will result in better career choice of students in librarianship in Federal Unity schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between career orientation and career choice in librarianship among final year students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria is hereby rejected. A statistical figure of (r =.370; p < 0.05) shows that the P value is less than 0.05 degree of freedom set for the inferential statistics, therefore, the reason for rejecting the stated null hypothesis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

RQ.1: Level of career orientation among final year students in Federal Unity schools, Lagos State, Nigeria

The findings of the study revealed that there is average level of career orientation among final year students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. This implies an adequate orientation of students on their choice of careers. This was, in contrast with the findings of this study, Mvungin (2009) and Mbilinyi (2012) found out that the education system in Tanzania did not provide proper career guidance and counselling to the majority of students. This indicates a low level of career orientation for the students. This was in total disagreement with the finding of this study that concluded that the level of career orientation among secondary school students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria is high. Further analysis of career orientation of the study by Mvungin (2009) and Mbilinyi (2012) showed that the majority of students receive general information and orientation about social welfare and university policies once they join the university and that little information is given to them with regards to orientation and the requisite courses. These practices

could help to explain the challenges that arose in the Tanzanian economy in recent years as the students struggle to adapt to the complex and unstable employment industry.

Similarly, the findings of this study could not be corroborated by that of King (2003) who studied career orientations among young graduates in the United Kingdom. The author found that the endorsement of the 'new career' was limited. In line with these results, Pitcher and Purcell (2018) and Sturges, Guest and Machenzie (2000) found that United Kingdom graduates still had very high expectations of organisational career management despite the current rhetoric about career self-management. Also, Mayrhofer, Meyer et al (2006) showed with a sample of Austrian graduates that a preference for a traditional career was still widespread. Likewise, Grote and Raeder (2009) reported a prevalence of traditional career orientations in Switzerland. Maingi and Wasanga (2011) also attested to the fact that lack of awareness about what happens at the universities by many secondary school students limits their university course selection and career decision-making process as a whole indicating a low level of career orientation. These were in total disagreement with the findings of the present study which concluded that the level of career orientation of students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria is high.

RQ. 2: Career choice in Librarianship among final year students in Federal Unity schools, Lagos State, Nigeria.

The finding of this study revealed a below average level of career choice in librarianship among students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. This is connected with the fact that none of the mean of the students' responses was significant. It showed that they were not favourably disposed to the choice of librarianship as a career for them to pursue. This finding is consistent with the findings of Ismail (2012) who revealed that after assessing the perceptions of higher secondary students regarding librarianship as career choice, as well as their level of awareness and interest in librarianship as a career choice, it was discovered that the majority of students are unaware of the field of library science and rank librarianship as the least desirable career option.

According to the findings, school librarians should work harder to promote the profession as a favourable career option. In agreement with the finding of this study, the study conducted by Damilola, Ajayi, and Adetayo (2018) discovered that the majority of students do not have an interest in library and information science as a career, but they found themselves in it by chance and while they eventually enjoy the course, they would have preferred to choose something else. This proves that despite the improvement in the publicity and orientation about librarianship as a profession, high school students still find it difficult to pursue it as their dream career.

An earlier study by Busayo (2006) did not fail to establish the true state of things in terms of the choice of librarianship as a career for high school students. The study also agreed to other previous and more recent studies on it. The author's study was carried out on a total of 1228 students from eight Nigerian LIS schools. It was found, that the majority of the respondents learned about library science from their mentors, parents and relatives. This submission leaves a bitter pill in the mouth to swallow for those in the librarianship profession as it shows that it is hardly a first choice career for any student.

This was further corroborated by Issa and Nwalo (2008) who reported that the bulk of the students (61.6%) did not choose the LIS programme as their first choice, they ended up as a last option in library schools. Furthermore, (38.4%) of student respondents said that previous library-related employment experience influenced their decision to pursue the LIS programme. The study concluded

that despite the increasing popularity of LIS programmes among the respondents, it remains largely unpopular among the prospective undergraduates in Nigeria, in comparison to other academic programmes such as accountancy, medicine and law.

Also, in line with findings of the study, Igbinosa (2007) noted that people, particularly students, do not want to pursue a profession in librarianship. This is due to their ignorance of the reality that librarians are the brains behind every other discipline's success story. Igbinosa (2007) went on to say that with the growth of information technology, librarians' jobs have expanded to include curator, programmer, consultant, webmaster, database manager, and analyst, among others. Salaam and Owolabi (2010) suggested that in order to attract more secondary school graduates into librarianship, library science should be taught in all Nigerian secondary schools and the Librarian's Registration Council alongside Nigerian Library Association should launch a full-scale public awareness campaign about librarianship as a noble profession.

H0₁ Significant relationship between career orientation and career choice in Librarianship among final year students in Federal Unity schools, Lagos State, Nigeria.

The finding of this study revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between career orientation and career choice among secondary school students in Federal Unity Schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. This is consistent with the outcome of the study carried out by Kimiti and Mwowa (2012) on the dilemma of career choice among secondary school students. The authors established a significant relationship between career orientation and career choice. It was further revealed that students make their career choices based on the information they received from the career counsellor or teachers.

The student acknowledged the fact that they were more knowledgeable because of the availability of information on careers available in their schools. The findings affirmed that the provision of career orientation services positively influenced students' decision on their career choice. Also, results from a study by Racho, Wambiya, Aloka and Raburu (2014) concur with other studies and affirmed that students' career awareness had significant relationship with students' career decisions. A study by Lugulu and Musoga (2013) found out that career orientation provided in schools was inadequate to enable students make informed career choices. Since the success of students making informed degree programmes choices depends on the level of career awareness. Gitonga (2013) affirmed that insufficiently prepared teachers and poorly equipped career guidance resources were the causes of career decisiveness among students in secondary schools.

In the same vein, Yusuf's (2019) earlier study agreed that limited knowledge of occupations and range of alternatives available often leads to unrealistic career aspirations. Maingi and Wasanga (2011) also attested to the fact that lack of awareness about what happens at the universities by many secondary school students limits their university course selection and career decision-making process as a whole. Thus, Garnesby (2013) pointed out that adequate career information resources and provision of professional career guidance and counselling at all education levels and direct or indirect exposure to work experiences from early stages of life play a vital role in career development.

Conclusion

The study resolved that career orientation in Librarianship is crucial to the possibility of secondary school students taking a decision on career choice in librarianship. An increase in the career orientation in Librarianship among secondary school students will result in the increase of their career choice in Librarianship. As long as the issues affecting career orientation are not well addressed, this will lead to a decline in the career choice in Librarianship.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Managements of federal unity schools should implement policies and programmes that will improve the career choice of students in Librarianship. They should employ qualified professionals librarians who could help them take advantage of the opportunities that abound in Librarianship.
2. School/ teacher-librarians should as a point of duty continue to create awareness on Librarianship as a noble profession.
3. Librarians employed in federal unity schools should consciously educate students on prospects in Librarianship in order to instill willingness in students about the profession.
4. Secondary school students should avail themselves of adequate information on Librarianship as a profession such as the job opportunities and career prospects which are obtainable in the profession.
5. Librarians should do more to project the image of their profession to secondary school students. More orientation programmes should be organised by professional bodies on Librarianship. They should facilitate the formal inclusion of library hour in secondary schools.

References

- Anagbogu, M. A., and Nwokolo, C. N. 2010. *Guidance and counselling in primary schools*. Lagos: Mark New World.
- Ayiro P. L. 2016. East Africa: Career choices: Dilemmas facing varsity students. <https://www.theeastafrican.co.ke/tea/ea-universities-guide/career-choices-dilemmas-facing-east-african-varsity-students-1349048>.
- Boitt, M. L. J. 2016. Evaluation of the challenges in the implementation of the guidance and counselling programme in Baringo country secondary schools , Kenya *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7.30: 27–34.
- Busayo, I.O. 2006: Career in Librarianship: The experience of academic librarians in Ekiti and Ondo States of Nigeria. *Library Progress International* 26:1, 1-9.
- Damilola, A, B; Ajayi, S, A., and Adetayo, A. J. 2018. Factors influencing the career choice of library and information science student's in Federal Polytechnic Ede, Osun State. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 1871.<http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1871>.
- Egbo, J.O.E. 2015. Guidance and counselling: A creativity for promoting sustainable wellbeing and adjustment of secondary school students in Nigeria. *British Journal of Education*, 3, 10: 49-57.
- Garnesby, S. 2013. *Career Planning and Development: The Path towards Your Dream Job*. New York: Create Space Independent Publishing Platform.
- Gitonga, F.N. 2013. Decisiveness in career choices among secondary school students in Kiambu West district- Kiambu county, Kenya. Unpublished thesis, Kenyatta University
- Grote, G and Raeder, S. 2009. Careers and identity in flexible working: Do flexible identities fare better? *Human Relations*, 18, 326-339.
- Ibrahim, R., Olaka, P. J.O., Wambiya, P., and Raburu, B.O. 2014. Perceptions on the role of guidance and counselling programme on Kenyan secondary school students' career decision making. *Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 4.6:301.
- Igbinosa, I. O. 2007. University of Benin students' perception of library and information science profession. *Nigerian Library Link*, 5.1: 74-82.
- Issa, A. O., and Nwalo, K. I. N. 2008. Factors affecting the career choice of undergraduates in Nigerian library and information science schools. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*, 18.1:23-31.
- Lugulu, A. & Musoga, J. M. (2013). Factors That Influence Selection of Undergraduate Degree Choices By Students in Public Universities In Kenya: A Case Study of Moi University, Kenya. Retrieved on 1/10/2023 From [Http://hdl.handle.net](http://hdl.handle.net).
- Kimiti, R. P., and Mwova, M. M. (2012). The dilemma of career choice: a case of students of Kenyan secondary schools. *Scholarly Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*. 1:3. 357-368.
- King, M. A. 2003. Comprehensive school counseling program: Counselor and principal agreement. *Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation*, Mississippi State University, Starkville.
- Kiweewa, J. M., Knettel, B. A., and Luke, M. M. 2018. Incorporating comprehensive counselling and guidance models into school curricula in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Int J Adv Counselling*, 40.133–147
- Loan, D., and Van, N. 2015. Career guidance in secondary schools: A literature review and strategic solutions for Vietnamese Rural Areas. *American International Journal of Social Science*, 4.5:135 -143.
- Low P. K. 2009. Considering the challenges of counselling practice in schools. *International Journal for the Advancement of Counselling*, 31:71- 79

- Maingi, L., and Wasanga, C. M .2011. Factors affecting career certainty among university students. *Kenyan Journal Of Guidance, Counselling and Psychology* 1: 1, 84 – 91.
- Mayrhofer, W., Steyrer, J., Meyer, M., Strunk, G., Schiffinger, M., and Lellatchitch, A., 2005. Graduates career aspiration and individual characteristics, *Human Resource Management Journal*, 15:1, 38-56.
- Ministry of Education. 2010. Education and career guidance (ECG) syllabus for secondary: Student Development curriculum division. Singapore. Retrieved August 20th 2021 from [https://www.moe.gov.sg>syllabuses>files-2014-education-and-career-guidance-\(secondary\)-syllabus.pdf](https://www.moe.gov.sg>syllabuses>files-2014-education-and-career-guidance-(secondary)-syllabus.pdf)
- Mushaandja, J., Haihambo, C., Vergnani, T., and Frank, E .2013. Major challenges facing teacher counselors in schools in Namibia. *Educational Journal*, 2.3:77-83.
- Mbilinyi, G. 2012. *Determinants of career decision making among secondary school students in Tanzania*. Master dissertation University of Dar es Salaam.
- Mvungi, G. 2009. *School-based factors influencing students' choice of teaching science as career: the case of government secondary schools in Ilala district*. Master dissertation University of Dar es Salaam
- Ogundele A. G., and Feyisetan C. T. 2014. Impact of vocational guidance in addressing the choice of vocational and technical education among Nigeria youth. *Open Science Journal of Education*. 2.5: 56-60.
- Ombaba, S., K, F.N. Sindabi, A.M. and Asienyo, B.O. 2014. Adequacy of career guidance resources in secondary schools in Nakuru, Kisii and Migori Counties, Kenya. *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, 6.4:921-928
- Omoni, G. E. 2009. *An overview of guidance and counseling in essentials of guidance and counselling*. Krisbec Publications: Delta State.
- Oraegbunam, N. M. 2008. Guidance and counseling: A missing link in the pre-primary and Primary education in Anambra State. *International. Journal of Educational Resources Development*, 3.1: 19-27
- Oye, N.D, Obi. M. C, Mohd T.N, and A. B Gawadawa .2012. Guidance and counseling in Nigerian Secondary Schools: The role of ICT. *I.J. Modern Education and Computer Science*, 8: 26-33.
- Pitcher, J and Purcell, K. 2018. Diverse expectations and access to opportunities: Is there a graduate labour market? *Higher Education Quarterly*, 52: 2, 179 – 203.
- Quadri, M, 2018. Influence of career choice on professional and job commitment of librarians in selected libraries in Oyo and Ogun States, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (E-Journal)*.
- Racho, I., Wambiya, P., Aloka, P. J. O., and Raburu, P. 2014. The status of career awareness among selected Kenyan public secondary school students. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*; 4:6, 301-312
- Salami, S. 2009. Relationship between work values and vocational interests among high school students in Ibadan. *Nigerian African journal of educational research*, 5: 2, 65 – 74.
- Savickas, M. L .2011. *Career counseling*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Sovet, L., and Metz, A. J. 2014. Parenting styles and career decision making among French and Korean adolescents. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 84, 345–355
- Sturges, J., Guest, D., and Mackenzie D. K. 2000. Who's in charge? Graduates' attitudes to and experiences of career management and their relationship with organizational commitment, *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology* 9:3, 351-370.

- UNESCO. 2002. Handbook of career counselling: A practical manual for developing, implanting and assessing career counselling services in higher education settings. Retrieved: 2nd August 2021 from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0012/001257/125740e.pdf>
- Wambu, G., and Fisher, T. A. 2015. School guidance and counselling in Kenya: Historical development, current status, and future prospects. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6:24-32.
- Watts, A. G., and Fretwell, D. H. 2004. Public policies for career development: Case studies and emerging issues for designing career information and guidance systems in developing and transition economies retrieved August 20th 2021 from: WorldBank.<http://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/546071468763805157/pdf/285980PAPER0LLLDevelopingCntrs01public1.pdf>
- Watts, A. G., and Kidd, J. M. 2000. Guidance in the United Kingdom: Past, present and future. *British Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 28:485-502.
- Yusuf, S., Muraina, K. O and Jamiu, M. S. 2019. Improving guidance and counseling services for effective service delivery in Nigerian secondary schools: implications for stakeholders in education. *Journal of Multicultural Studies in Guidance and Counseling*, 3.1: 75-89